

Life Cycle Assessment On Membrane Bio-Reactor And Activated Sludge Systems

Surya Pratap Singh^{1*}, Aman Pandey¹, Rahul Sharma² and Meena Kumari Sharma¹

1. Manipal University, Department of Civil Engineering, Jaipur - 303 007

2. Manipal University, TAMPI School of Business, Jaipur - 303 007

Water is required for agriculture, industrial purposes and to meet the thirst of increasing population. Due to the increasing demand for water, recycling of water has become a necessity. The treatment of wastewater solves two purposes, that is meets the increasing demand for water and reduces wastewater pollution. So wastewater treatment is required due to depletion of water sources. It came early in the 1900s and became popular since then. There are many types of wastewater treatment processes. The paper focuses on two types of wastewater treatments, namely the conventional activated sludge (CAS) process and membrane bioreactor (MBR) treatment plants and their life cycle assessment (LCA) from beginning to end. In CAS process, the physical stage includes different coarse and fine screens which filter wastewater and is further treated in an aeration tank with bacteria whereas MBR process (submerged MBR) has membrane or cassettes submerged inside secondary tank made of polymer for effective cleaning. One way of comparing them can be LCA of both the treatment plants where they are to be compared based on the impact they cause on the environment by their emissions and resources they consume during their whole life from the day they were constructed and maintained during operation. The assortment and analysis of the results and the impact on the environment of the system establish an environmental profile called life cycle assessment.

KEYWORDS

Membrane bioreactor, Conventional activated sludge process, Life cycle assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

Though 70% of the planet is covered by water, only 2.5% of it is fresh. Of this, nearly 70% is frozen at ice caps and glaciers in Antarctica and Greenland. The rest is present as soil moisture and in deep underground aquifers [1]. As a result, a very short percentage of water on the planet is available for human consumption. Water distribution in the world is very uneven while the amazon alone carries 16% of the global runoff, the arid and semi-arid zones of the world that constitute 40% of the landmass and receives only 2% of the global runoff. This uneven distribution results in conflict as agriculture, industries and domestic sectors compete with each other for the scarce resource [2]. We fail to benefit from these resources because of poor water management, exploitation of surface and groundwater and pollution caused by untreated or partially treated effluents discharge into water bodies.

Wastewater from the homes termed as domestic sewage which has on a larger view creates two problems, first, the water is being wasted and water pollution

invites diseases and degrades the environment. This water comprises of dissolved and suspended impurities and can cause harmful diseases. Wastewater harms the aquatic life and it's a hazard to human health. The different types of treatment phenomena can be conventional activated sludge systems (CAS), conventional activated sludge systems with filtration treatment (CAS-TF), immersed membrane bioreactor (MBR), external membrane bio-reactor, etc. Further, the paper revolves around CAS and MBR systems [3].

1.1 Conventional activated sludge process

A typical treatment for municipal wastewater treatment is generally broken into primary treatment (removal of floating and settleable solids), secondary treatment is typically the aerobic biological treatment process by which bacteria oxidize the organic matter in the wastewater, producing cell mass (sludge) and carbon dioxide [4]. Lastly, tertiary treatment filters the remaining constituents to improve the quality of the final outlet.

1.2 Membrane bioreactor process

MBR process is divided into two types, namely a submerged system in which membrane is submerged deep in the tank with its pore size in between 0.1-0.4 mi-

Figure 1. Membrane bioreactor flow-chart

creens. The other type is in which the membrane is outside the tank and permeate is let into the membranes using a vacuum pump. This type of system requires a high amount of pumping power to keep the velocities high to prevent membrane fouling and high pressure to force the water through the membrane [5]. These systems have a larger footprint than submerged systems due to the outside placement of the membranes. Due to this, the decision was made to install a submerged MBR system at Manipal University, Jaipur using a 0.45 micron pore size polyvinyl difluoride hollow fibre membrane. Water flows from outside to inside the fibres and is collected at the ends and finally fed into a collection chamber. Hollow fibre membranes have been widely used for submerged MBRs, both for industrial and municipal areas, where they are more preferred for bigger plants based on their low aeration energy requirement [6].

The focus of this paper is to assess the impact on environment by the MBR and CAS process by performing LCA on both which includes four steps, namely defining goal and scope; the life cycle inventory stage which includes all environmental input and output; the life cycle impact assessment which helps us understanding the environmental relevance of all the inputs and outputs and lastly the interpretation of the study.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Membrane bioreactor installed at Manipal University

There are five MBR (STP) plants in the Manipal, Jaipur campus out of which we performed on the 1 MLD capacity which was installed at the hostel site used to treat wastewater and making it feasible for gardening and flushing the toilets. The process starts with two

screens, that is coarse and fine screens with a pore diameter of 16 mm and 6 mm, respectively which don't allow the passage of particles larger than the pore size. And then there is a collection tank which transfers raw sewage to oil and grease skimmer which separates coarse particles and oil and grease in the tank. The water is then fed to the equalization tank which moderates the flow and flows with the average velocity enters into bioreactor tank after passing the mini screen which separates the particle greater than 2 mm (Figure 1). The process in the bioreactor tank is similar to that of CAS process where inside aeration tank organic pollutants are removed by bacteria in the presence of oxygen. Then the MBR process comes which differentiates it from the CAS process as a membrane screen is installed which removes 99% of the impurities where pore size is of ~ 0.4 microns.

The submerged membranes are placed directly into the existing aeration tank where it acts as a barrier for remaining impurities in the effluent further cleaning it and latter removed by suction pump leaving the suspended particles in tank. Also, the reverse activated sludge process involves some bacteria which goes from sludge tank to bioreactor tank again where bacteria perform extra cellular enzymatic reaction converting the nature of organic matter. The portion of the mixed liquor suspended solids (MLSS), that is eating the incoming food is referred to as the MLVSS. The volatile solids concentration in a sample of mixed liquor will consist mostly of microorganisms and organic matter. As a result, the volatile solids concentration of mixed liquor is approximately equal to the number of microorganisms in the water and can be used to determine whether there are enough microorganisms present to purify the water [4]. Then the sludge left in the tank is passed in the sludge holding tank where it is further centrifuge with a polymer which separates biomass (mixed liquor) and water. Further, biomass is removed using a sludge pump. Hence, biomass produced at the end can be used as fuel and for making compost reducing the impact on the environment as compared to the CAS system.

2.2 Conventional activated sludge system

The CAS system or the conventional wastewater treatment is divided into three stages, namely primary, secondary and tertiary under which primary removal covers the initial screening and sedimentation process. The secondary stage is the aerobic decomposition of organic matter by bacteria in the wastewater producing sludge and CO_2 . In the suspended growth systems, the bacteria are there in the aeration tank and can be said to be mixed liquor suspended solids (MLSS). Blow-

Figure 2. Conventional activated sludge process flow-chart

ers then supply air to it to supply the necessary oxygen [4]. The bacteria is then separated from the pure water which is then brought to the next treatment while sludge is drawn in the aeration tank for reuse. The third treatment or tertiary process is the final process after the secondary treatment which improves the quality of the purified water by further filtration (Figure 2).

3. LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Life cycle assessment (LCA) of a product evaluates and ascertains the profile of the system and defines the impact on the environment. We can perform many things with LCA, like product or project development and improvement, strategic planning, public policy-making and marketing and eco-declarations [7]. International Organization for Standardization (ISO-14040) describes the whole LCA.

3.1 Goal and scope

The primary goal is to compare two treatment processes: CAS treatment with MBR treatment process, their impact on the environment and best alternative are chosen. The screening approach is taken into account for LCA and the impact of the capital goods on both the processes with their operational and maintenance requirement is considered. The function and the functional unit were determined. The functional unit, in this case, is 1 L of treated or processed wastewater. The limitations of the plant tell us the production stages and processes being considered within the LCA study. The temporal boundaries consist of input and output flows of material and energy resources for the operation of the systems over 15 years span. The greenhouse gas emissions were considered as both of the treatment plants release CO_2 . In both cases, the sludge disposal was monitored carefully and the impact on the environment was observed.

About MBR treatment, the data was calculated for five months on influent and effluent for BOD (biochemical oxygen demand) and COD (chemical oxygen demand) ratio of which represents the ability of the microorganism to treat the organic matter and if this biological process is suitable for cleaning the wastewater. Higher the ratio of 5 day BOD and COD, higher the biodegradability of the wastewater; TSS (total suspended solids) which is the amount of solids retained by the filter. Its high concentration in the water is a hazard to anyone using it. Lastly, for the nutrient removal efficiency, the phosphorus and nitrate were calculated. For CAS treatment, all the above-mentioned data was taken from nearby Delawas sewage treatment plant (62.5 MLD) which works on the activated sludge process.

The treatment of MBR is better than CAS because of high removal efficiency of organic matter and also due to more number of bacteria in the tank which due to which the MBR can take more of contaminant. Also, the energy required to treat the water in both the scenarios, the processes going inside the individual tank in both the cases and their impact on the environment was considered even if some of the processes going inside the plants had a same environmental profile. The membrane tank and membrane structure and its transportation cost was considered.

3.2 Inventory analysis

After knowing the goal and scope, all relevant values were equalized as per the functional unit to make the options comparable. Thus, the effluent quality was carefully monitored from both the plants, that is MBRs or CAS plants. The construction inventory was prepared with the materials required for plant fabrication, transportation, processes used for raw material processing and energy consumption. Operational inventory was prepared by measuring electricity consump-

Figure 3. Comparative efficiency of MBR and ASP systems

tion, air emissions and emission to water and soil. The construction details have been brought up from plant manufacturer (Suez), whereas operational and maintenance cost were asked from the officials operating the plant. The BOD and COD values of the outlet in both the plants were quite similar to the quality of pure water is a function of the amount of energy used in the treatment process. There is a direct correlation between them as more energy is required for a clean outlet. In running the treatment process, this factor was palpable and its quality would determine for what purpose it can be used. All the data of the MBR treatment plant installed at Manipal University, Jaipur was obtained from Suez company.

Talking of the MBRs, the main parts/units were under consideration which are the fine and coarse screen, the different steel tanks, the centrifuge tank with cationic polymer and the membrane cassettes made of polyvinyl difluoride. The amount of material used in these parts and the transportation distance from their point of manufacture to MBR plant location were all considered. The material used for membrane structure is made up of polyvinyl difluoride though it was not available in the SimaPro databases but was assumed to be made of hollow cellulose fibers [4]. These membranes structures have a life of around three years and so it can be said there is a need to change membrane for around 5 times during the life of the treatment plant. The submerged type of MBR system consists of a microfiltration membrane with pore size ranging from 0.1- 0.4 microns [8]. These membranes are submerged in the secondary tanks, with the permeate being drawn into the membranes using vacuum capable pump [9]. The materials when used in making membranes with specific dimensions have a minimal impact according to SimaPro. Lastly, the land acquisition was not into consideration under LCA because with the construction of the treatment plant the landscaping was also kept in mind.

4. COMPARISON OF MEMBRANE BIOREACTOR PLANT AND CONVENTIONAL ACTIVATED SLUDGE

Inventory flows are considered over system boundaries. The data obtained from Manipal University, Jaipur for MBR plant shows that the plant serves daily around 10,000 people. With 1 million litres of water treated daily, the total consumption per day would be 1000 m³. Apart from all this, the energy and chemicals used and the production of sludge was also kept into consideration. The MBR plant functions over electricity provided by JVVNL from the grid and solar panels installed at Manipal University, Jaipur campus. The power consumption for a day goes about 900-1000 kWh, which means solar energy harnessed per day will not be enough. Also, this plant requires maintenance due to its membrane fouling wherein the membrane sludge deposition takes place which needs to be backwashed after every 8 min which consumes more power and after every 3 months to be cleaned by sodium hypochlorite or sodium hydroxide for efficient cleaning.

The CAS plant considered treats around 62.5 million L per day in the area of Delawas (Pratap Nagar, Jaipur) which targets around 2.5 lakh people. The CAS system turned out to be futile as earlier discharge from hotels and industry waste polluted the road, choked the drains harming the environment. Now the biodiversity and water quality has improved and due to production of biomass, every month 2-3 lakh is saved in the bills. The infrastructure parameter of the CAS system was quite similar to that of the MBR system since the inventories were similarly constructed. In this too, the energy and the chemicals and production of sludge was kept under consideration as the biomass produced from sludge used as an energy source for sewage treatment plant. The sludge produced in the MBR system was used to make compost which provides humus to the soil. This is the information from the Manipal University, Jaipur campus MBR plant whereas, in the Delawas STP, the biomass produced from sludge was further used to generate electricity [10].

4.1 Energy requirement in both the cases

The MBR system installed at Manipal University, Jaipur site works on the electricity provided by local grid, that is around 85% and rest 15% is produced by solar insolation installed inside the campus whereas ASP system at Delawas site consumes around 25-30% from local grid and remaining from the biogas produced when it comes to daily operation and maintenance of the plant.

4.2 Physico-chemical comparative efficiency both systems as a whole

The comparison of both the ASP system and the MBR system were to be determined based on their removal efficiency in terms of physico-chemical parameters (Figure 3). The total suspended solids is measured when the sample is filtered, dried and weighed and both the systems hold good efficiency in removing the total suspended solids from wastewater. However, due to small pore-size membrane, the MBR system has quiet good efficiency over it. The BOD is the dissolved oxygen used by microorganism in the presence of air to consume biodegradable organic matter. The 5 day-BOD calculated in the MBR system was 19.52 mg/L whereas in CAS system it was 27 mg/L. The COD is the dissolved oxygen in which microorganisms consumes both biodegradable and non-biodegradable matter. The COD is a very important parameter and here MBR system dominates over CAS system as efficiencies can be seen.

The most important parameter which differentiates MBR system from CAS system is the nutrient removal efficiency which makes the effluent suitable for discharge into lakes, oceans preventing eutrophication whereas CAS system lacks in the field of nutrient cleaning. Lastly, the most probable number of MBR system is turning out to be very low ~ 4 when compared to CAS efficiency which is very low as compared with MBR. Also, there is a big problem of sludge bulking inside CAS system which occurs when sludge does not settles when it is passed from aeration tank causing a big problem as in MBR system the sludge settles down with time (~ 60 mL in 30 min) which makes it easier as water is used for further treatment and sludge for making compost or biomass.

4.3 Impact assessment

The impact assessment is measured in terms of three parameters, namely the human health, ecosystem quality and resource and landuse. The effect on human health was measured in terms of its most probable number where MBR is dominating the CAS system and due to low MPN efficiency, the CAS system invites water borne disease leading to a health hazard. Both the plants follow the aerobic treatment process, producing carbon dioxide which has enough global warming potential harming the ecosystem but on a comparable basis, the efficiencies were reiterated and was observed that the inability of the CAS system to clear the nutrients contributes to a major impact on the environment as the discharge when goes to streams forms a dark layer of nutrient destroying aquatic life and harming the ecosystem quality. The MBR treat-

ment does not have secondary clarifier like that of the CAS system rather than it employed MBR for cleaning process with less of landuses making it better than the CAS system. On comparing the resource use, the energy consumption of the MBR system is more as it requires high energy and the power required to run it only works on 25-30% of renewable energy as installing solar panels. Whereas the CAS system works on biogas produced which is around 60-65% energy required to run the CAS system.

4.4 Data interpretation

The MBR system is a simple and reliable alternative wastewater treatment method [11]. The treated water from the MBR plant of the study area is being successfully used for flushing and gardening inside and nearby Manipal University, Jaipur campus. The sludge produced is converted into compost used as humus for the soil. The space requirement is less as compared to CAS system as the need for settling tanks is eliminated. MBR plant can be quickly installed, commissioned and maintained by trained personnel.

5. CONCLUSION

After seeing all aspect of LCA in this paper, it seems that the MBR technology can be effectively used for wastewater treatment in decentralized wastewater treatment for reuse and disposal of treated water onto water bodies with lesser pollutant load whereas CAS system comes with a lot of environmental loads. They have minimal operator interface and smaller carbon footprints than CAS systems. However, MBR systems have high installation and operating costs and there is still uncertainty in the membrane cost due to availability many types of membrane material and also the problem of fouling of MBR system pushes it one step backwards.

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